

**JUGLANS REGIA L.NI MIKROKLONLASHDA FLOROGLUSINOLNING STIMULLOVCHI
 SIFATIDA O'RNI**

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Grek yong`og`ining (*Juglans regia L.*) O`zbekiston uchun mahalliy hisoblangan genotiplarini mikroklonal ko`paytirish jarayoni klomlash bosqichi samaradorligini oshirish uchun turli konsentratsiyadagi floroglusinolning ta`siri o`rganildi.

Kalit so'zlar: Grek yong'og'i, mikroklonal ko'paytirish, floroglusinol, mahalliy genotiplar.

Kirish. Grek yong`og`i (*J. regia L.*) qimmatbaho oziqaviy qiymatli o`simlik bo`lishi bilan birga, manzarali va yog`ochbop daraxt sifatida muhim ahamiyatga ega o`simliklardan biri [1,2,3]. Markaziy Osiyo, shuningdek O`zbekiston ham yong`oq kelib chiqish markazlaridan hisoblanadi va yong`oqlarni sanoat miqyosida yetishtirish uchun qulay iqlim sharoitiga ega [4,5]. Hozirda Akademik M.Mirzayev nomidagi bog`dorchilik, uzumchilik va vinochilik ilmiy tadqiqot instituti tomonidan bir qancha istiqbolli mahalliy yong`oq genotiplari o`rganilgan, so`ngra mikroklonal ko`paytirish va plantatsiyalar yaratish uchun tavsiya etilgan [6,7,8]. Yong`oqni mikroklonal ko`paytirish xususiyatlari o`rganilgan va bu jarayonga juda ko`p omillar, jumladan genotip ham ta`sir ko`rsatishi aniqlangan [9,10,11]. Floroglusinol (FG) o`simlik to`qimalarining kulturasiga murakkab ta`sir ko`rsatadigan lignin biosintezining tabiiy shaklidir (12). Bir nechta tadqiqotlarda FG auksin yoki sitokinin ta`sirini stimullashi mumkinligini ko`rsatadi (13,14,15). Ushbu tadqiqotda, istiqbolli mahalliy genotiplarni mikroklonal ko`paytirishning proliferatsion bosqichida samaradorlikni oshirish uchun floroglusinolning ta`siri o`rganildi.

Materiallar va usullar.

O'simlik materiallari

Akademik M.Mirzayev nomidagi bog`dorchilik, uzumchilik va vinochilik ilmiy tadqiqot instituti dan grek yong`og`i (*J. regia L.*) ning uchta istiqbolli genotipi tanlab olindi: "Ideal" navi (N41°36.157; E70°05.767) va "202YaKT formasi" (N41°36.157; E70°05.767), PDM 23 formasi; ' (N39°73.852; E66°73.381). Apikal meristemalardan olingan materiallar 2 mg/l BAP va 0,01 mg/l IBA bilan to`ldirilgan 10 ml DKW [16] oziqa muhiti bo`lgan shisha probirkalarga (150 × 20 mm) individual ravishda ekildi va standart fotoperiod sharoitlarida saqlandi. Kontaminatsiyalangan yoki nobud bo`lgan eksplantlar, shuningdek, ko`p miqdorda fenol ajralishi kuzatilgan probirkalar sanaldi va tashlab yuborildi.

Klonlash: bir bo`g`imli eksplantlar 96 mg/l Fe-EDDHA, 1,5 mg/l BAP, 0,01 mg/l IBK, 30 g/l saxaroza bilan to`ldirilgan va 5,5 g/l Agar bilan gellangan (DKW) [16] Driver va Kuniyuki oziqa muhitida o`stirildi. Avtoklavlashdan oldin pH 5,7 ga o`rnatildi. Eksplantlarning yangi mikronovdalar hosil bo`lish jarayonini oshirish uchun turli konsentratsiyalarda: 0,0, 0,2, 0,4, 0,6 va 0,8 mM floroglusinol ishlatilgan va har bir genotip uchun kallus massasi (g), mikronovdalar uzunligi va yangi mikronovdalar soni aniqlandi.

Natija va muhokamalar. Natijalar shuni ko`rsatdiki, uchala genotipda ya`ni, Ideal navi va PDM23, 202YaKt formalari eksplantlarida floroglusinol konsentratsiyasi ortishi bilan ularda kallus massasi, mikronovda uzunligi va soni ortdi. Ideal navi va PDM23 formasida new microshoots soni yuqori natijani, mos ravishda 3.96 va 3.54 ni namoyon qildi. Ammo, 202YaKT formada esa konsentratsiya ortishi bilan yangi mikronovdalar hosil bo`lish jarayonida sezilarli o`zgarish kuzatilmadi(1.6) (1-jadval).

1-jadval. Turli xil FG konsentratsiyasining yong`oqning mikroskopik kallus hajmi, o'sishi va yangi novdalar shakllanishiga ta'siri

Genotip	Floroglusinolning konsentratsiyasi (mM)	Kallus massasi (g)	likronovdalar uzunligi (sm)	Yangi mikronovdalar soni
Ideal	0	0.14±0.06	1.41±0.24	1.81±0.13
	0.2	0.32±0.08	2.35±0.32	2.62±0.17

	0.4	0.57±0.13	3.12±0.35	3.56±0.16
	0.6	0.75±0.18	3.38±0.54	3.84±0.21
	0.8	0.92±0.16	3.87±0.62	3.96± 0.38
PDM23	0	0.23±0.06	2.34±0.52	1.52±0.08
	0.2	0.47±0.12	2.90±0.56	1.96±0.12
	0.4	0.81±0.21	3.66±0.32	2.48±0.23
	0.6	1.04±0.17	4.18±0.62	3.27±0.27
	0.8	1.18±0.24	4.14±0.31	3.54±0.33
202YaKT	0	0.16±0.05	1.66±0.22	1.12±0.24
	0.2	0.34±0.04	2.16±0.49	1.34±0.11
	0.4	0.58±0.13	2.45±0.28	1.56±0.14
	0.6	0.66±0.18	2.25±0.35	1.62±0.15
	0.8	0.74±0.12	2.28±0.42	1.60±0.21

Shuningdek, floroglusinol konsentratsiyasi 0.4 mM dan ortib borishi bilan, o`rganilgan ko`rsatkichlar miqdor jihatdan oshgan bo`lsa-da, eksplantlarning sifat ko`rsatkichlari birmuncha pasaydi, ya`ni defoliation va barglar sarg`ayishi va qorayishi kuzatildi (1-rasm). Klonlash bosqichida floroglusinoldan foydalanish MJ209xRA klonlari uchun samarali deb topilgan va olingan natijalar ushbu tadqiqot bilan mos keldi (17). Shuningdek, yana bir qancha tadqiqotlarda Liahoe-1 va boshqa yong`oq genotiplarini mikroklonlashda o`xshash natijalar qayd etilgan (18,19,20).

A

B

C

1-rasm. 0.4 mM (A), 0.6 mM (B), 0.8 mM (C) Floroglucinol konsentratsiyasida ko`paytirilgan PDM23 forma eksplantlari.

Xulosa. Tadqiqot natijalariga ko`ra, optimal konsentratsiyada qo`llanilgan floroglusinol yong`oqni mikroklonal ko`paytirishning klonlash bosqichida eksplantlarning yangi mikronovdalar hosil qilishiga ijobiy ta`sir ko`rsatadi. Ushbu tadqiqot natijasiga ko`ra, Ideal navi, PDM23 va 202YaKT formalari uchun 0.04mM konsentratsiyadagi floroglusinol optimal deb topildi.

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